

PARENTING CHILDREN WITH NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS: AN INNER JOURNEY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 10

Pages: 1090-1104

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1832

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11208455

Manuscript Accepted: 04-20-2024

Parenting Children with Neurodevelopmental Disorders: An Inner Journey

Zyrene Anne A. Pabrualinan,* Karen Marie P. Garcia, Trixia Anne A. Reyes

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Focusing on how parents cope with their child's new diagnosis the goal of this research was. The research focused on how parents acted both before and after learning about their child's diagnosis. The informants were five pairs of parents: 5 mothers and five fathers were chosen with criteria set as used purposive sampling. The data was collected via in-depth interviews with each parent and by observing their actions and reactions to their kid at home. It was then analyzed using qualitative data analysis. Data analysis revealed four overarching themes: parental stress, parental engagement and perception, parental quality of life, and parental coping strategies. Their reactions to the diagnosis, the impact it had on their daily lives, the difficulties they encountered in adjusting to life with a child diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder, the stress they felt while watching their child's aberrant behaviors, and how they coped with these issues are all detailed in the evidence. In addition, most informants are eager to adapt and support their children's growth and development. The study's author recommended more research on the emotional toll that parents take after receiving a child's diagnosis.

Keywords: *neurodevelopmental disorder, parent journey*

Introduction

A parent's experiences raising a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder show a complex and highly challenging life. Evidence shows the incidences of the increase in neurodevelopmental disorders here in the Philippines. In 2019, the data showed that around 1.2 million or one in every Filipino have autism (Commission on Human Rights, 2019). As the prevalence of individuals with neurodevelopmental disorders increases, many families, especially the parents, are starting to understand the said condition.

A neurodevelopmental problem often comes with its own unique set of challenges for parents. There are many steps to any journey, and the first step for every parent is receiving the news that their kid has been diagnosed with a disease. This is known as the diagnostic stage. Here, parents begin to consider their options beyond the doctor's advice and consider how they feel about the situation. The discovery step follows. This is a place where parents look out for their children's best interests. Here is where parents learn the most about their kids' personalities. These may offer more evidence to parents who sought the advice of a developmental pediatrician on warning signs they had previously seen. Here, parents of a kid with a neurodevelopmental issue get to know their child on a deeper level. During the accommodation stage, parents begin to explore other solutions, including therapy, that may support their child's improvement. In the success stage, after meeting their kid's requirements, parents work to help their child become more self-reliant and socially adaptive. Some parents still struggle to instill in their children a sense of autonomy, particularly when it comes to learning how to care for themselves. Nevertheless, they persist in their efforts, aided by other experts. When parents have a clear idea of where they want their kid to go in life, they enter the following phase, advocacy. Here, parents may incorporate what they've learned about parenting from the beginning of their journey into their daily lives. Finally, parents in the ally stage seek out other parents going through the same thing by joining support groups. In addition to providing support, these organizations may assist parents raise awareness of their children's illness (George, 2022). They went through these steps as they dealt with their kid who had a neurodevelopmental condition.

As they navigate parenthood with a kid who has a neurodevelopmental problem, it's important to observe the parents' actions and reactions. In many ways, the actions of parents whose children are young and normally developing mirror those of parents whose children have a neurodevelopmental problem. Having a kid with a neurodevelopmental problem requires a great deal of patience and hard work from parents, since they are taught everything. Parents of grown-up children with neurodevelopmental problems must be always by their side due to the extreme dependence of these children. Parents have more freedom to teach them things and then leave them when they're ready, in contrast to children who grow normally. In this case, the parent's actions may evolve over time in response to their child's diagnosis and, more importantly, their child's current developmental needs.

The operationalization of parental conduct is based on the work of Grusec and Davidov (2015). Parents' actions have an impact on their children's social development. Another option is to focus on the ways in which the kid may develop cognitive, emotional, and social abilities that will serve them well in their future relationships with others. "Behavior" covers a lot of ground. The researcher wanted to discover how parents with a neurodevelopmental problem interacted with their kid daily, so they did qualitative study. Some common threads that surfaced throughout the research should provide light on how other parents interact with their own children. When it comes to the day-to-day functioning of a kid who has a neurodevelopmental problem, parents are crucial. Thus, it is them who bear the brunt of any problems pertaining to their kid. A child's requirements might take several shapes when they have a neurodevelopmental issue. Parents need to fill out a lot of forms for their kid to improve, including one from the developmental pediatrician, forms for treatments, forms for medication, forms for food intake (if prescribed), and many more.

An infant with neurodevelopmental disorder may experience challenges in performing daily activities for the remainder of their lives (APA, 2013). A definitive cause for a neurodevelopmental disorder has yet to be determined, and ongoing research continues to explore potential etiological factors. The researcher manages numerous cases of neurodevelopmental disorders, including intellectual disability, autism, and ADHD, among others, in her capacity as a behavior therapist. Parents who encounter their child with neurodevelopmental disorder often seek assistance. Occasionally, parents wonder why they have a child with such a condition. The researcher consistently observes the daily interactions between a parent and their child who has a neurodevelopmental disorder in their capacity as a behavior therapist. This statement holds true for parents whose child was recently diagnosed by a developmental pediatrician. In her capacity as a behavior therapist, the researcher observes the strategies employed by these parents to manage the daily obstacles they encounter while caring for their child who has a neurodevelopmental disorder. It encompasses potential modifications to each facet of their existence. Such as their marital status, professional life, personal relationships with their children and others, and even their self-perception as a parent who merely desires a routine existence for their family.

The study's informants comprised the parents of a child who had recently received a diagnosis of neurodevelopmental disorder. The research investigated the parental reaction when their child was recently diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder. All were regarded equally, irrespective of their socioeconomic standing, provided they were in the company of their offspring. Additionally, the study included parents residing in the same household, irrespective of their relationship status. The participants were collected throughout Metro Manila by the researcher and were engaged in virtual interviews at a time and day of their choosing. Additionally, each of the selected informants was in good mental and emotional health, which could have an impact on the research procedure. Within a year, the children of the informants received new diagnoses in accordance with the developmental pediatrician's criteria. Understanding the behavior of parents in their interactions with children who have recently been diagnosed with neurodevelopmental disorders was the purpose of the study. The way parents discover that their infant has a pre-existing condition may differ. Furthermore, the researcher inquired about the respondents' attitudes and behaviors regarding their daily lives when caring for a child diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder.

Additionally, these informants are formulating a diagnosis for their child, according to the study. Through an understanding of parental conduct, the researcher discerned the coping mechanisms that the informants employed in managing their child with a neurodevelopmental disorder, in addition to the therapies their child was undergoing. As far as available literature and studies conducted by Filipino researchers are concerned, there is a dearth of research in the Philippines concerning the experiences of parents whose child has recently been diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder. Despite the rising prevalence, most of the research focuses on the behavior of the child rather than the parents. Additionally, as the prevalence of neurodevelopmental disorders in children rises, more individuals are becoming cognizant of these conditions. There are currently a variety of interventions that can assist parents in gaining a deeper comprehension of their child's condition. Due to this rationale, the current investigator undertook a study to augment knowledge and understanding regarding the experiences of these parents regarding their recently diagnosed child with a neurodevelopmental disorder.

Research Questions

The following questions helped the researcher explore and knew about the parent's journey in handling their child with neurodevelopmental disorder.

1. How do parents describe their behavior toward their child before knowing their child's diagnosis?
2. How do parents describe their behavior toward their child after knowing their child's diagnosis?
3. How do parents describe their challenges and experiences interacting with their children?
4. What are the coping mechanisms of the parents in dealing with the situation?

Literature Review

In its first form, Mowder (2011) referred to the theory as PRDT. When thinking about parenting, the parent development theory (PDT) considers the crucial social role that most parents play. To analyze how parents really raise their children, it is essential to have a firm grasp of traditional parental responsibilities. When thinking about parents and their children, it's important to consider the many social roles that parents play, including friends, teachers, employers, and workers. Everyone expects parents to behave like parents while they're with their kids. Consequently, the PDT analyzes the function of parents as a whole and as individuals, and it defines the role that parents perform in their children's life. PDT also shown the potential for parenting approaches and methods to evolve and transform over time. Furthermore, PDT stresses the importance of parents' responsibilities and how they relate to one another. Because every person is unique, it's helpful to know what their parents expect of them to comprehend those duties (Mowder, 2011). Parents' mentality, life experiences, and ability to comprehend their kid shape the role they play in their connection with their child.

Parents' views of their own roles might shift as their children mature and evolve. Similarly, a newborn needs constant attention. But their parental demands also begin to change as kids get older and begin to experience a sense of self-reliance. Parents devote a great deal of time and energy to caring for their newborn children, attending to their needs such as feeding, diapering, caressing, and holding them when they scream. Their developmental requirements shift once again as babies enter the toddler and preschool years. More and more, parents are putting their attention on supporting their children, leading them through routine school activities, and watching out

for them when they go out on their own adventures. The parent-child bond changes and adapts as the kid develops. But let's say there's strife between family members, such parents, and children. The bond between parents and children might be impacted as a result (Levine, 2021).

The research team was able to learn more about the changes in parent behavior after a child's neurodevelopmental condition diagnosis because to PDT. Just as the parents' responsibilities change as their kid develops in a normally developing child's role changes, so too does the parent's position in PDT. The parent's involvement in teaching their kid life lessons gradually fades as a normally developed youngster grows and becomes more self-reliant. But the parent's function may remain constant or evolve with time in a kid afflicted with a neurodevelopmental disease. By analyzing how parents' perspectives could exhibit various changes over time, the PDT contributed to a better understanding of the parenting problem. Considering their own experiences raising children, they adapt and react accordingly. Child specialists, such as developmental pediatricians and other medical professionals, may use the PDT to better understand how parents' approaches to parenting impact their children's growth and development.

In addition to Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) work on coping mechanisms, Biggs, Brough, and Drummond's (2017) theory of coping mechanisms will also be useful to the research. The theory has been categorized into two groups based on two parameters: the approach's macro-and micro-analytical nature, and whether it is trait-or state-oriented. A person's attitude toward a problem and their search for solutions to that issue are central to trait-oriented theory. Simultaneously, the state-oriented approach focused on how a person copes and the results of his coping tactics.

Using these two criteria, Lazarus, and Folkman (1984) argued that trait-oriented theories and macro-analytic theories are similar. One of the three types is repression-sensitization, which helps people deal with stressful situations. The individual has excessive anxiety because of their tendency to ignore or downplay the severity of the situation. As a result of their increased curiosity in the source of stress, the following coping mechanism, monitoring, and blunting, is successful. The monitoring blunting construct is where the Model of Coping Modes gets its start. Additionally, it has ties to the repression-sensitization theory, which states that people respond to their immediate environment.

Caring for a kid with a neurodevelopmental impairment is their priority as a parent. Every day, they may be under stress, thus they need to know how to handle their kid. They all deal with it every day, but in different ways. When other parents learn about their child's situation, they go into denial. By refusing to acknowledge that their kid had a disability, they attempted to evade the issue. Meanwhile, there are parents who act swiftly to get assistance and who research ways to support their children. In this case, the coping methods hypothesis put out by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) might be useful as it examines potential ways in which the parents cope. Other than that, the parents deal with the problems they face daily.

The research also benefited from Erik Erikson's idea of the psychological growth phases. According to Erikson, there is a natural progression from infancy to maturity in terms of personality development. There is a societal crisis that occurs at each level. Regarding character formation, it may have both beneficial and bad effects. Since it pertains to the individual's psychological needs, Erikson considers this crisis to be of a naturalistic character. Furthermore, the idea asserts that a healthy personality is the end outcome of successfully completing each stage. Concurrently, an unhealthy personality will emerge if the stage is not completed. Between the ages of 0 and 1, children go through Erikson's phases of trust and distrust; between the ages of 1 and 3, they go through autonomy and shame. There is initiative vs. guilt between the ages of three and five, industry vs. inferiority between the ages of five and twelve, identity vs. role confusion between the ages of twelve and eighteen, intimacy vs. isolation between the ages of eighteen and forty, generativity vs. stagnation between the ages of forty and sixty-five, and ego integrity vs. despair between the ages of sixty-five and death (McLeod, 2018).

It is very unlikely that a kid diagnosed with neurodevelopmental problems will be able to reach these milestones in their development. Because their kid is struggling to go to the next level, it is imperative that these parents provide them with an abundance of care and attention. Here, Erikson's psychosocial stages of development were useful since they mapped out the phases that a kid with a neurodevelopmental condition goes through between the ages of three and ten. The research was able to observe that a child's chronological age and developmental age can overlap due to their disease, because it focused on the psychosocial phases of development. When signs of neurodevelopmental problems began to emerge in their kid throughout the formative years, the parents began to question how their child was behaving in comparison to normally developing children. Confirmation that their kid had a neurodevelopmental problem was a watershed moment when they decided to seek professional support and intervention to change their conduct towards their child.

Methodology

Research Design

Lincoln (2005) classifies the research as qualitative, with an emphasis on a naturalistic approach. Qualitative research involves seeing events in their natural habitat and analyzing them according to the meanings individuals ascribe to them. Understanding the perspectives of all individuals, all groups, and all cultures is the fundamental purpose of qualitative research, which relies on first-hand accounts from informants. On top of that, the locals are being examined in their native habitat. The study's use of qualitative research methods

allowed it to focus on the informants' daily lives and their actions. The results were derived from the study's essential real-life experiences and extensive qualitative investigation. It was an unstructured interview, so the subject could use their own words and go into detail as they liked. As a result, the researcher had a better grasp of the informants.

In addition, the study used the phenomenological method, a qualitative research strategy that pays close attention to the lived experiences within a specific group (Creswell, 2013). In this method, having a detailed description of the characteristics of a phenomenon is the end aim. Subjects who have first-hand knowledge of the phenomena under investigation are contacted via in-depth interviews. Answering general questions is the goal of the interview procedure. It is also possible to utilize other types of data, such as papers, and surveys. This aids in comprehending the occurrence or event through the eyes of the public. In addition, phenomenological research is characterized by itself. Thorough interviews and discussions should be carried out initially. Data may be gathered via journals, sketches, or observations in some research. This research similarly follows the conventional practice of using a small sample of informants. The next step is to ask the informants open-ended questions so they may provide a detailed account of the event from their point of view. Like ethnography, phenomenology is based on first-hand accounts from study participants. These four facets of a lived experience—lived place, lived body, lived time, and lived human relations—are also central to phenomenology. The information gathered is of a qualitative nature, and the analysis involves an attempt to spot developing themes and draw conclusions based on the informants' perspectives on their experiences (Holloway, & Galvin, 2017). Since this study focused on parents' experiences, a phenomenological research approach was adopted. The phenomenological investigation may go farther into this and provide a more detailed description.

Participants

These are the parents, both mother and father of a newly diagnosed child with a neurodevelopmental disorder, and they take good care of the child together. The informants were five pairs of parents: 5 mothers and five fathers. The parents have no existing psychological issues or concerns. There should be no need to be attended to by a professional—alternatively, therapy or medication and health risks that affect their participation in the study. The parents were free from any health concerns. There were no restrictions in terms of age of parents, educational background, and socioeconomic status. The child with a neurodevelopmental disorder of the parents should be aged three years to ten years old. Other therapists and another therapy center referred the informants to the researcher.

Instruments

The following are the tools the researcher will use in conducting the study. These will be the researcher's guide in achieving the purpose of the study. First was the interview process. The researcher discussed with the informants what the study is, its goals and objectives, and the content. It further helped the informants as they were oriented on what kind of study, they had participated in. It consisted of only one session and lasted for 1 hour only.

Procedure

Upon gathering the data, the researcher needed for the study, the researcher first had an evaluation of the possible informants that were included in the study. The researcher looked for parents with a newly diagnosed child using an assessment report from the Developmental Pediatrician. In the assessment report, the impression and the assessment date should not be more than a year for it to be considered newly diagnosed. The assessment report includes the recommendations for the child to undergo an intervention like ABA therapy, speech therapy, and other related therapy interventions. Parents of these newly diagnosed children are living together. They also have a personal bonding with their child. That is why they were qualified for the study.

The researcher got the informed consent given to the chosen and qualified informants. After that, informed consent was given to the parents. The researcher discussed with the parents the benefits they would get from the research if they were willing to continue participating. Upon agreeing, they already signed informed consent, and the study started already. A voice recorder was also used during the research process. The voice recorder was used during the interview and with the consent of the informants. This tool helped the researcher interpret results as the parents did not agree to have them recorded with their faces. The researcher did the interview virtual interview. There is no need to get a permit from the barangay if it was done in the convenience of their home through virtual interviews. The informants were also allowed to ask questions at any time, precisely when they wanted to clarify some things related to the research study.

The researcher also informed the parents that the interview was only one session and was conducted on their own choice of day, date, and time. The appointment for interviews was in their available time. In addition, the researcher interviewed the parents separately to observe the sameness or differences in the parent's behavior in finding out the child's diagnosis. The interview shall be terminated if answers have been saturated and when the informants gave repetitive answers. The researcher has also ensured that the informants' information and identity are kept confidential. There was also no forcing to participate as the researcher ensured that the informants agreed to the study. To show gratitude to the informants for participating in the study, the researcher gave a simple token such as food delivery when the researcher interviewed the parents.

Ethical Considerations

Upon the review of this research study by the ethics committee, the following ethical considerations were observed in gathering data to make sure that this research study followed the right procedure and was not harmful to society or an individual. The researcher as a Behavioral Therapist did proper assessments in choosing the informants and made sure that they were all qualified as they are also not suffering from any mental health condition which may affect the research study. In addition, the researcher made sure that the chosen informants were from different branches and therapy centers to avoid double or multiple relationships with the informants. All the data, including the results, were detailed, and was seen in this research. When working with informants, there was an agreement that all the said information would be consistently kept confidential. As to this, the researcher used code names in putting the informant's profile and life stories. An informed consent form was also given to the informants before they started participating in the study. A developmental pediatrician report was also needed in the study. For this reason, the researcher made sure that a letter of permission was given to the doctor informing them that their assessment report would be used in the process of conducting the research study. Taking care of the study was also done to avoid mistakes. The researcher reviewed the study carefully and critically to ensure that the results will be credible.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses all the data gathered by the researcher through the one-on-one interviews conducted with the informants. Thematic analysis and eidetic representations were used based on the themes that showed from the statements of the informants' responses to the interview questions. The last part of this chapter discusses the researcher's insights on the said representation of themes.

Life Stories of the Informants

For the researcher to fully understand and comprehend the situation, it was also necessary to inquire about their background. The informants of this study are five pairs of parents, five mothers, and five fathers of a newly diagnosed child with neurodevelopmental disorder, all diagnosed in less than a year. The informants' responses to the screening process were also included with the inquiries about their personal life. In addition, the informants' life stories are an essential part of the study, and here, much emphasis was placed on the study's importance.

Informants 1- The "coach" and the "player."

The "coach" and the "player" have been married for eight years. They are both working, although the mother has been on a work-from-home setup ever since. At the same time, the father is a seaman who has stayed with them for two years since the pandemic started. According to his father, his work was affected during the pandemic. He took up online classes now to improve his work as a seaman. They have two children, and the oldest is the one diagnosed with Autism and Combined Type ADHD. She is already seven years old. Before discovering their child's diagnosis, the mother took care of their child most of the time as the father worked as a seaman and would return after six months.

The father would stay for three months, then return to work again. Before they knew about their child's diagnosis, she noticed some deviant behaviors of her child, which she started comparing to his nephew, who also had ADHD. Due to the mother's observations, she started talking to his husband and discussed what she thought their child had. Although the father initially became in denial, he was convinced that maybe their child needed help. The incident wherein they saw their child having a meltdown while studying with her tutor- that she kept on crying hurt herself and lay down on the floor. It happened when their child was six years old. Because of this, the mother sought help immediately and went to a developmental pediatrician. After finding out the diagnosis, they started different therapeutic interventions. The father, who initially had difficulty accepting the challenges, eventually accepted it and supported what they needed to do to help their child. He also added that if before, he and his wife were fighting aggressively, now that they learned about the diagnosis of their oldest child, the fights are lessened and quieter. Their family members also accepted it and helped them by adjusting their responses towards the child and being more understanding in dealing with their child. The mother also added that they still go outside and travel just like before. They treated their child as a normal kid who needed social interaction for her to also act normal, just like the other kids.

Informants 2- The "super" nanay and tatay.

These "super" nanay and tatay are parents of two children with a neurodevelopmental disorder. They are twins and are four years old already. They were diagnosed at three years old, and both had an autism spectrum disorder. The informants are not married and live with partners. The mother is a teacher, while the father has an on-call job. Before finding out their child's diagnosis, they were both aware of the red flags their children were showing. Although they were wondering if maybe it was just part of growing up as they saw their twins were progressing, especially during their early developmental years. According to the mother, the twins were attentive, produced babbling sounds, playing toys, and even recognized the alphabet when they were one year old. However, as time passed, they observed that the twins started not to talk, producing sounds but no words, and could no longer recognize alphabets. Meltdowns such as crying and laying on the floor were also mainly observed. They also added that sometimes, the mother was left taking care of the twins as the father was working and was a stay-in worker. Hence, it was tough for the mother to assist the twins as she was alone and working as a teacher. Because of these, they immediately decided to go to a developmental pediatrician. From there, they found out

that their children have autism.

They added that even if their children are twins and have the same diagnosis, they still differ regarding skills; one is more severe than the other. After finding out about the diagnosis, they both adjusted the setup they had at home. The father stopped working, and the mother adjusted her work hours at school for them to be focused on taking care of their twins. The mother also added that the pandemic somehow helped her focus on her children as they are on a work-from-home setup. It was challenging as the mother also lessened going out even if she needed to go and meet her co-teachers. Because of the diagnosis, they started to seek therapeutic intervention even if they struggled financially as the mother was the only one working. The mother also started reading other research about autism to understand their children more, especially when handling them whenever they have meltdowns or tantrums.

Informants 3- “Better late than never” parents.

The parents have been married for eight years already. They have two children, and the oldest was the one diagnosed with autism. He was seven years old. These parents started therapy intervention first before they went to a developmental pediatrician. The father works as a marketing specialist, and the mother is a housewife. Most of the time, she is the one who is always with the children as the father is working. According to them, he was attentive during their child's early years, babbling sounds and even reciting alphabets. However, as their child grew, he started to change, and red flags were seen, such as poor attention, does not make any sounds, and does not follow instructions. They also started observing frequent crying and meltdowns. Before, they thought their child might act and behave "maturely" in time even if they started to observe these red flags. In short, they usually treat it.

However, as time passed, they noticed their child was not improving, and the red flags they saw were still present. Because of that, they started to seek therapy intervention when the child was four years old. However, the parents admitted they were still in denial, so they did not continue the therapy and tried teaching their child at home. Until their child turned six years old, they decided to go back to therapy as they were starting to feel worried about their child's condition. A year passed, and they were thoroughly convinced and decided to visit a developmental pediatrician. Their child was diagnosed with autism when he was seven years old. From that point in their lives, both parents started to accept the diagnosis by consistently attending therapy sessions gradually. The father adjusted his work hours to accompany his wife and their child to every therapy session. They also added that because of their child's diagnosis, they became more hands-on and focused on helping their child. They even instructed their other child to always look for his brother, who has autism, every time they play outside. These parents hope their child will soon improve and be an average child like the others.

Informants 4- The “assertive” nanay and tatay.

These parents have been married for eight years and have two children; their youngest child was the one diagnosed with autism. The father worked in a work-from-home setup before the pandemic started, and the mother was a housewife. Long before they had confirmed their child's diagnosis, these parents already observed some red flags they knew they should be focusing on. At three years old, they noticed that their son was still not yet talking compared to their other child, who started talking at an early age. As they observed these red flags, the mother immediately studied their child's red flags. From that point, they were convinced that they needed to go to a doctor. However, due to the pandemic situation, their resources became limited. Locked down started, and they were not allowed to go outside.

Two years had passed, and they finally had their visit to the developmental pediatrician when their child had already turned five years old. From there, they confirmed that their child has autism. After finding out the diagnosis, the mother admitted that it was painful and hard to accept that their child has autism. She started questioning herself and compared how he handled his first child and his youngest child, who had autism. Despite this, the mother started seeking different ways to help their child, such as different therapeutic interventions.

Moreover, because the father was the only one working, the mother asked for financial assistance from different government agencies to support their child's therapy. She even did her continued internet research about what they could do to help their child improve. The mother was very persistent, which the father agreed with the most. According to the father, having a child with autism is challenging because they must deal with it daily. Aside from that, it is hard because it is expensive. He was grateful for his wife as she consistently looked for people who could help them support the finances of their child's needs. He also said that the other family members are also helping. However, because of the significant expenses, it was not enough.

The father also started using their situation to spread awareness and help other parents. He said that he shares his everyday experiences handling his child whenever he talks to his friends. The father was also accepting as he focused on the solution and was optimistic that their child would improve. Because of what these parents are doing, their children started showing improvements, although they still needed continuous therapy intervention.

Informants 5- The “newbie” parents.

Compared to other informants, these parents recently found out about their child's diagnosis. They have been married and have three children. Their youngest, a four-year-old child, had been diagnosed with an autism spectrum disorder. That is when they decided to visit a developmental pediatrician as they were already convinced of the red flags they consistently observed towards their child. The parents are both working from home since the pandemic started. The mother is a marketing manager, and the father is an IT. Since they

were always at home, they could see and observe their children, especially their youngest child. Before they went to the doctor, they were already convincing their selves that it would only be a speech delay, but the diagnosis turned out more. Informants admitted they were surprised about the diagnosis as they somehow expected it would be the same diagnosis as their firstborn.

They said they also brought their first child to a developmental pediatrician to check him as he was not still talking at three years old. However, their first child improved as time passed and was now very talkative. So, they were surprised when they found out their youngest child had autism. After finding out the diagnosis, the mother admitted that she is in the stage of denial until now. She kept on thinking and even recalling how they cared for their youngest to have the diagnosis with autism. She also added that she is still in the process of coping as she got hurt when they found out about the diagnosis of their child.

Eidetic Representations

In this section, the motifs that surfaced during the interviews conducted with the informants are examined. Four overarching themes were identified through the investigation, each with its own set of subthemes. The initial one is tension, which encompasses anxiety, denial, and comparison as subthemes. Parental involvement and perception follow, comprising the subthemes of adaptation and assertiveness. The quality of life of parents subsequently demonstrated awareness as a subtheme. Parental coping is the final subtheme, comprising acceptance, resolution, and support. Each of these themes originated from the statement's purpose. The initial purpose statement of the study was to inquire about the behaviors exhibited by the informants that prompted them to contemplate seeking the services of a developmental pediatrician for their child.

The subsequent depiction in Figure 2 illustrates their emotions and reactions in the form of a volcanic eruption. The respondents were queried regarding the way their conduct towards their infant altered after receiving the diagnosis (the act of chess facing the mirror, as depicted in Figure 3). As depicted in Figure 4, the third purpose statement, which addresses the difficulties and potential consequences of having a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder on various facets of the parents' existence, is represented by a variety of objects placed on a table, including a book, tea, and candle. The final purpose statement inquired about the parents' strategies for managing the challenges or difficulties they face when caring for their infant. The parents' level of functioning is visually depicted as a pathway, as shown in Figure 5.

Table 1. *Eidetic Representation of Themes*

<i>Cluster</i>	<i>Themes</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>	<i>Symbol</i>
Behavior towards the child before knowing the diagnosis of their child?	Stress	Denial Comparison Fear	
Behavior towards the child after knowing the diagnosis of their child?	Parental Engagement and Their Perception	Adjustments Assertiveness	
Challenges and experiences in their interaction with their child?	Quality of life of parents	Awareness	
Challenges and experiences in their interaction with their child?	Coping Strategies of Parents	Acceptance and Solution Support system	

Figure 2. Stress

“Nung una, nung nalaman nga s’ya may gano’n, masakit, sobrang sakit, kasi sabi ko, “Bakit?” ‘Di ba? Marami kang tanong eh. ‘Di ba ang rami mong tanong? Kasi sabi nila baka daw sa genes, eh wala naman saming ganun.”

- The “assertive” nanay and tatay

Stress is common to all people. Stress can come from different sources in which a person starts to feel overwhelmed by the pressure in their surroundings (Mental Health, 2021). Being a parent and managing a family is where a person could feel stress at times. Most informants felt stress before, during, and after finding out their child’s diagnosis. Many of them started to ask themselves “why” as they started to feel the pressure.

They compared their child with other children of the same age whose behaviors are not the same as their child. Why they are still not talking, why they always cry, why their child cannot follow simple commands, and so on (DSM 5).

With stress comes fear and denial of what is happening, especially when a person is trying to cope with the pressure he is experiencing (Ankrom, 2020). The informants started to feel scared not just for their families but most especially for their children. Their fear comes from thinking of their child in the future and what will happen if their child still has the same behaviors that others may not understand. Although the human body is designed to experience and react to stress, this should be controlled to avoid escalating into a bigger problem in the future (Cleaveland, 2021).

Figure 3. Parental Engagement and their Perception

“Sa akin kasi parang I know na it’s something I can live with and alam ko na it’s something that we can control, and we can correct. Hindi ‘to ‘yung tipo na lumpo na s’ya forever or... Gano’n ‘yun sa ‘kin eh. Ako kasi si, “Oh ano na next na gagawin natin?”

- The Coach and the Player.

Engaging with the child’s life is critical to having a good relationship with him. It engages the child’s learning at home, at school, and environment. It discusses how parents and other practitioners can help their child’s development and give a supportive environment (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014). Most informants actively engage with their children, especially when they discover their child’s diagnosis. They started to seek help- look for different therapeutic interventions, and research the next step they should be doing in helping their child. Having an engagement with the child shows more outstanding commitment as a parent. (Goodall, 2014).

Figure 4. Quality of Life of Parents

“Tapos wala namang ano.. Nangyaring sisihan, ganun.. or sa bata.. Sa awa kumbaga ano naman blessed pa rin ako kasi kumbaga wala naman kami ganung eksena sa bahay. Kumbaga, naiintindihan din naman ng mga tao sa bahay na ito ay hindi naman parang yung factor yung parang factor kung sa mother or kaya sa parents kasi wala pa talagang cause. Yung mga tipong ganun tsaka parang

wala din naman mangyayari kapag nagsisihan kayo or yung ganun, diba? Or mag-turuan kayo 'baka sainyo nang-galing yan' yung mga ganun wala naman.

- The “super” nanay and tatay.

“And then of course ‘yung nangyari din made us kumbaga stronger pa ‘yung faith kasi ‘yun na talaga ‘yung moment na wala ka namang magagawa kun ‘di give your best, ‘yung mga therapy, gan’yan. Kumbaga it’s a miracle na lang talaga for this one to be okay.”

- The “newbie” parents.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), quality of life (QOL) is a person's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live. It connects to their future goals and societal expectations (International Encyclopedia of Public Health, 2008).

Most of the informants showed a significant effect. They changed their life views after discovering their child's diagnosis. They became fully aware of their child's condition and even want to use this to spread more awareness. At the same time, help other parents who are also experiencing the same situation. Having a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder is challenging. However, these informants used this to still look forward to the future and spread hope for others in the same situation.

Figure 5. Coping Strategies of Parents

“Kasi number one lang naman dyan actually wala naman pong proper or right term for coping up. So, number one is talagang ang pinaka number one dyan is talagang acceptance. Number one cure daw sa mga cases ng mga ganyan bata is acceptance of the parent. So ganun lang po talaga. Kailangan naming tanggapin, gawin kung ano yung advice ng therapist, kung ano po yung dapat naming gawin sa bahay, pag work with, kung pano po kami makakatulong. Syempre hindi lang naman po natin dapat iasa sa therapist lahat e, diba?”

- Better late than never, parents.

According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, coping is how a person deals with and overcomes problems and difficulties. Informants showed sameness in coping with the challenges of having a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder. They all started with acceptance-acceptance of the situation they have and what their child is. Parents tried to process the difference between the things they want for their child and the diagnosis to which they are also adjusting (Healey, 2022). Informants choose to see the positive side of the challenges they are facing with their children and seek help as soon as they can. Although for the informants, it will be a long and will not efficiently process, they are willing to do all they can just to help their child. In addition, aside from their partner or family member, the informants also started joining different support groups in which they found people who had the same experience. Many factors contribute to coping, including having a sound support system. They are people that a person likes to respect and trust. They can be family members, friends, teachers, neighbors, or someone experiencing the same thing. What is essential is that the people he feels comfortable talking to about what someone is experiencing would get the support that a person may need. Research has shown that having a social support system can positively impact his mental health (Mental Health First Aid USA, 2020). In addition, a support system is an excellent way for the informants to cope as they face these challenges in life. There will always be a person or people who will understand and listen to their situation.

Eidetic Insights

The analysis of the collected data revealed the interior journey of parents who have a child with neurodevelopmental disorder, as well as the inner journey of the researcher during the study.

The parents began to question certain deviant behaviors exhibited by their child, which were atypical in comparison to those of other children. They were concerned about the red indicators that their infant was exhibiting, which prompted them to seek further evaluation from the physician. Upon visiting the physician and receiving the prognosis, the parents began to experience anxiety. They were overcome with apprehension, denial of what they had just learned, and sorrow as they confronted numerous obstacles in caring for their child. Notwithstanding the anxiety they experienced, parents of recently diagnosed children developed a heightened awareness of their child's ailment and initiated the process of pursuing assistance. They also complied with the physician's instructions. They dedicated time to assist their child in improving, conducted additional research regarding their child's diagnosis, and enrolled their child in various therapy interventions. Instead of altering their approach to their infant, they developed a greater sense of obligation to

participate in their child's growth and progress. They had a stronger relationship as parents and were more supportive of one another as they confronted these life challenges.

Furthermore, most of the parents are already managing the challenges they are facing. Gradually, they conditioned themselves to embrace it so that they could devise a course of action and progress. They recognize that the only way to assist themselves in coping with the diagnosis and provide additional support for their child is to embrace it. A support infrastructure is also essential for these parents. They solicited assistance from one another and their additional relatives. They considered it to be of great assistance, as it would enable them to comprehend their child's situation better. Participating in various support organizations comprised of parents who share similar circumstances can also be beneficial in terms of coping mechanisms. They became members of a support group where they could obtain encouragement and a variety of advice regarding the care of their child who had a neurodevelopmental disorder. This environment fosters the avoidance of judgment and encourages parents to assist one another in managing the difficulties they encounter while raising their child.

The researcher has encountered both difficulties and rewards throughout the course of conducting this study. As the subject matter of the study was highly intimate, locating informants during the data collection phase was somewhat difficult. However, the researcher observed that certain parents have a desire to assist others who have been through a similar situation by divulging their personal journey of managing a child diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder. The researcher learned a great deal from the interviews regarding the perspectives of the various parents regarding how to care for their children with neurodevelopmental disorders. While the researcher had encountered various accounts of this situation before, it was nonetheless an unprecedented and overwhelming experience. Their personal experiences prior to and following the discovery of their child's diagnosis were examined in the study. Several parents were observed to be in tears by the researcher as the informants recounted their voyage during the interview. As the interview progressed, the researcher was astounded by the parents' ability to cope with the situation. Furthermore, the researcher was honored to be granted the participants' insights and to have faith in them as they recounted their ordeal with caring for a child diagnosed with a neurodevelopmental disorder. Furthermore, the researcher was filled with joy and appreciation for these parents' decision to embrace their child and provide it with the necessary assistance, namely therapeutic intervention, as a means of coping. Aside from this, the researcher discovered that most individuals are now more cognizant of the neurodevelopmental disorder because of the parents' shared interior voyage. Various interventions become more permissible and accessible as a result. The researcher experienced a sense of satisfaction as she believed that by granting these parents the opportunity to express their inner voyage, she had assisted them in some way.

Analysis

Table 2. Stress

Theme	Statement	Informant
Stress	<i>Syempre una, natakot ako eh, kasi sa age n'ya kasi. Tapos babae pa s'ya parang bakit ganon na 'pag naiinis s'ya. Ano, nasasaktan n'ya sarili n'ya tapos, parang, hindi mo s'ya ma-control. 'Yun talaga. Parang takot talaga ang unang ano sa 'kin.</i>	The "coach" and the player.
	<i>Tapos, mga one year old na, ano..diba. Naririnig na namin sila mag identify ng letters, ng numbers, syempre naexcite ka na kasi nakakapagsalita na, diba? Tapos pag dating ng mga two..parang, bakit ganun? Bakit parang walang improvement? ang ibig kong sabihin yung parang 'uy yung anak mo ba ganito?' 'siyempre wala ka naman ibang pagtatanungan, diba? Kumbaga makikipag-compare notes ka sa ibang parents din. Yung mga nagdaan na dyan or kaya naman yung parang dumadaan yung parang, kasabayan mo yung parang 'hala, bakit ganun..'. 'bakit ganun, bakit hindi ano, tapos, syempre at the back of my mind, may ganun akong iniisip na) 'baka may something wrong dun sa mga anak ko. 'baka kailangan, ipaganito, may mga ganun ka. Pero syempre, hindi mo masyado ine-entertain yun sa umpisa ganun kasi, ayan. Continue pa rin ako sa pag tanong tapos yan, sinasabi naman nila sa akin na 'hindi, hintayin mo lang yan.</i>	The "super" nanay and tatay.
	<i>Syempre, medyo ako malungkot. Ganung sitwasyon na nangyari sa kanila di ko inaasahan na ganyan pero same pa rin naman, masaya pa rin naman kami. Kasi, andiyan sila eh.</i>	The "super" nanay and tatay.
	<i>Nung una, nung nalaman nga s'ya may gano 'n, masakit, sobrang sakit, kasi sabi ko, "Bakit?" 'Di ba? Marami kang tanong eh. 'Di ba ang rami mong tanong?</i>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
	<i>That's why 'yung changes so ngayon na-alarm kami and then talagang sad 'yung diagnosis. So, we are giving him time even if we are going upside down.</i>	The "newbie" parents.

In the most precise manner possible, the statements illustrated how the informants experience the "stress" associated with raising a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder. It is a form of tension characterized by an imbalance between the responsibilities and capabilities of a family in relation to the demands of family life. Put simply, they are the distressing occurrences that transpire within a family unit. They are also referred to as "family stress outcomes" (Thames & Thomason, 2007). As stated by the Mental Health Foundation (2017), an individual experiences tension at any given moment. We may experience a variety of additional bodily occurrences, including the onset of anxiety or pain. Most parents are apprehensive about-facing stigma, judgment, and inquiries regarding their child's future, such as whether or not they will recover. They are unable to help but compare their infant to the average

child as their anxiety increases.

Table 3. Parental Engagement and their Perception

Theme	Statement	Informant
Parental Engagement and Their Perception	<i>So ako, when it came to my daughter, iniyakan ko 'yung sinaktan n'ya 'yung sarili n'ya. 'Yun talaga, dun ako na-hurt kasi umabot kami sa point na nag-meltdown s'ya nang gano 'n, and I know how to handle it na already pero kung 'yung sa diagnosis, hindi ako. It was already accepted na sa akin kasi kumbaga, I already knew naman, nakita ko na agad eh, since may experience ako.</i>	The “coach” and the player.
	<i>Parang, tina-try ko siya i-take objectively, yung ganun kasi kumbaga, hindi naman bago sa akin yung ganung klaseng bagay. Kumbaga, aware naman ako na nakakakita naman ako ng ganun tapos, kumbaga, napag-aralan naman natin sa school yun. Yung ganun, yun nga lang, siyempre iba pa rin talaga kapag yung anak mo diba? Kaya yun parang. Kumbaga, may. Siguro, kung in-allow ko yung sarili ko baka naging denial ako kaya parang gusto ko as much as possible, objective ako dun sa situation kasi nga mahirap kasi kapag pag ano yung emotion mo syempre kasi diba, anak mo sila tapos diba kapag pinairal mo yung emotion mo, which is nandyan naman talaga, kasi di mo naman pwede syempre maisang-tabi yun pero kumbaga parang kumbaga parang mas iniisip ko na dapat objective din ako sa pagtingin ko sa kanila, kasi nga hindi naman din makakatulong kung magde-deny pa ako na 'hindi, sige. Wait pa natin.</i>	The “super” nanay and tatay.
	<i>Kasi alam mo, mahirap kasing maging in denial eh, kapag 'yung anak mo na 'yung gano 'n kasi kung magiging in denial ka, pa'no s'ya? Hindi s'ya ma-ti-treat. Walang treatment sa kan'ya, 'di ba? So lalaki s'yang gano 'n.</i>	The “assertive” nanay and tatay.
	<i>Actually syempre, to be honest, ang hirap. Kasi, hindi ko alam, hindi naman ako parang. I'm not professional with regards to.. To that kind of ano.. attitude...Syempre, bilang magulang, kailangan natin siya intindihin and then..like, normal na bata ganun pa rin namin siya tinatrato.</i>	Better late than never, parents.
	<i>In terms of feeling, 'yung feeling na parang mixed emotion eh kasi nga hindi ako nag-expect ng something positive para at least kung may negative things man 'di ba, madali ko s'yang ma-ha-handle. So, I think more on the preparation side lang siguro. Pinepre-prepare ko na 'yung sarili ko kaya hindi ko na masyadong nakita na... Hindi ko s'ya tiningnan as negative eh. Mas nag-focus kami on the solution eh. As much as possible, gusto sana naming maging extra careful, pero ang payo kasi sa 'min i-treat s'ya as normal eh. Pero syempre, you have to... 'Yung support mo mas nadagdagan kasi syempre 'yung iba nga 'yung kilos n'ya. Hindi nga s'ya normal unlike other kids, 'di ba? So, in terms of pakikitungo, same lang, normal. So 'di ko s'ya tine-treat na mayron s'yang ASD eh. Sa 'kin ah. Not sure kung makakatulong 'yon pero basta gusto ko s'yang tingnan na gano 'n.</i>	The “assertive” nanay and tatay.

According to experts, parent engagement is parents' and other professionals' way of sharing a responsibility to help their children. They learn and meet goals that can help the child improve, especially in areas with something to work on. Parent engagement happens when other professionals such as teachers involve the parents in school meetings or events, and parents show their support through having follow-ups at home. In this way, parents commit to doing what they can to help their children (Sheldon & Jung, 2015). For the informants, after finding out their child's diagnosis, they all immediately ask for help by giving their child therapy interventions. They also do their research about the diagnosis to know more about it. It also shows how these parents are willing to adjust to their child. They are willing to sacrifice some things, especially their finances, wherein they need to save more and prioritize therapy fees. Parents are assertive about what they need to do and are eager to find a solution immediately as they want their children to improve.

Table 4. Quality of Life of Parents

Theme	Statement	Informant
Quality of life of parents	<i>Kasi hindi na ako dumaan sa denial. Hindi ako dumaan sa... Kasi may phases 'di ba, but I saw that sa parents ko. With this kasi, kasi nga since I have an experience ever since sa brother ko, ako kasi nag-alaga do'n talaga eh.</i>	The “coach” and the player.
	<i>Actually, wala namang binago eh. 'Yun nga lang, may nadagdag na ah. Kung baga syempre, mas kailangan mong mag-focus sa kan'ya, sa attitude n'ya, sa bawat kilos n'ya, pero actually wala naman. Hindi naman. Nakakagalaw-galaw naman ako. Kung baga, aware din naman 'yung mga kaibigan namin kung ano 'yung meron sa family namin.</i>	The “coach” and the player.
	<i>Malaking bagay kasi 'yung nalaman namin kasi syempre sa 'ming mag-asawa natural 'yung minsan nag-aaway kami, gan'yan. Tapos ah since nung nalaman namin na gan'yan, mas nagkaron kami ng control sa isa't isa eh, na 'pag may away kami, pinag-uusapan na lang namin nang mahinahon 'di katulad dati na sumisigaw na ganyan, pero ayon ah... Saka mas maging, syempre... Kailangan... Kailangan naming, matatag kami sa isa't isa eh dahil para din naman kay baby.</i>	The “coach” and the player.
	<i>Sa work, nag-adjust nako sakanya. So,makikita niyo, kaming dalawa yung parating nasa</i>	Better late than never,

<p><i>therapy, nagsusundo, naghahatid kasi, ang una naming binigyan ng pansin yung oras na pag hindi namin ginawa yun ngayon, Kailan pa? Dahil kung mas nalate pa kami ng pagtrain mas mahihirapan kami in the future kaya mas maganda yung ginagawa mo na ngayon kahit na-late ka ng konti, pero mas binibigyan mo na siya ng pansin kaysa yung wala kang ginagawa. Kasi kung wala kang ginagawa at at pinapatuloy mo lang siyang gumagawa ng bagay na hindi normal sa katulad niya. So, parang binabalewala mo lang yun bilang isang magulang.</i></p>	parents.
<p><i>Tsaka tapos wala namang nangyaring sisihan, ganun or sa bata, sa awa kumbaga blessed pa rin ako kasi kumbaga wala naman kami ganung eksena sa bahay kumbaga naiintindihan din naman ng mga tao sa bahay na ito ay hindi naman parang yung factor yung parang, hindi naman parang factor kung sa mother or sa parents kasi wala pa talagang cause yung mga tipong ganun tsaka parang wala din naman mangyayari kapag nagsisihan kayo or yung ganun, diba? Or mag-turuan kayo 'baka sainyo nang-galing yan' yung mga ganun. Wala naman.</i></p>	The "super" nanay and tatay.
<p><i>Yung work, opo medyo naka.. May apekto. Naka-apekto kasi di tayo makalabas-labas, di makahanap ng trabaho, maski training, di tayo makapag training..kasi nga, sila at saka sa relationship naman namin ni Misis, wala naman problema ganun pa rin naman.</i></p>	The "super" nanay and tatay.
<p><i>Actually, sa social life ko, wala naman. Ginawa namin kasing mag-asawa na ano lang. Sabi n'ya sa 'kin, 'wag masyadong isipin. Normal life. Normal life. Kung ano 'yung dati, gano'n pa rin tayo. Actually, gano'n pa rin ginawa namin.Minsan mas binibigyan pa namin ng time talaga na lumabas, 'yung mga gano'n. Normal lang.</i></p>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
<p><i>It was parang buong lingo yata na hindi s'ya nawawala sa isip ko kasi finding the solution is easy, pero in terms of the financial stability, syempre you need to support. Hindi lang naman s'ya libre. Isa s'ya sa mga tinitingnan natin kung paano ba natin i-aano 'yan. Kung pa'no namin iraraos 'di ba, so syempre. Hindi na kami nakapag-budget eh sa gano'n so medyo biglaan. So ngayon, we're coping up pa. So 'yun 'yung sa work na talagang nakakaapekto s'ya. Iniisip mo 'yun eh. 'Yung factor, pero in terms of the affection sa kan'ya, sa relationship, wala naman masyado kasi nga, like I mentioned, more on the, na-prepare na namin. It was just that, paano namin i-e-execute. Mahirap kasi mag-execute eh nang kami lang. Actually thankful ako with my wife kasi syempre gumagawa s'ya ng paraan. Mga financial assistance, 'di ba? May mga gano'n s'yang ginagawa para lang makatulong din. So 'yun siguro. We pull ourself together lalo, especially 'yung eldest ko, ten na s'ya. Pero naiintindihan n'ya 'yung situation. Sabi ko naman walang mababago, but we have to be there for him kasi syempre we have to assist him eh all the time. So, we need to understand. Syempre minsan baka hindi namin maiintindihan, pati 'yung eldest ko, sa mga tantrums n'ya, but we have to be very patient lang about it.</i></p>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
<p><i>Sa social life, wala naman masyado. It's just mas naging open lang ako about it. So, whenever I have friends na ganyan so minsan nagkukwento ako sa kanila, hindi dahil to get sympathy, but to spread awareness na parang hindi mo s'ya mapapansin at first eh. Hindi mo s'ya p'wedeng ipagsawalang bahala. 'Yung social life, wala masyado eh. It's naging parang advocacy na naming mag-asawa eh. Hindi kami nagkukwento or nagsasabi para to get sympathy. 'Di rin naman namin s'ya parang ginagawang example na parang "Uy si may gan'to." Hindi, parang sinasabi namin para to... For them to check 'di ba, to prevent lang, especially dun sa mga friends namin may anak na rin. So 'yun.</i></p>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
<p><i>We really shifted na to balance it out. Talagang to shift it na mas madami 'yung time ko sana with the kid compared before. With my husband naman, after the diagnosis, he decided din na for us to go out regularly, every weekend, so 'Yun, magastos and then we don't Talaga Kasi naman go out because of the pandemic, pero since 'Yun lang din 'Yung one of the treatment na p'wede naming ibigay-to go out, eat together, have time with him, para ma-expose din outside.I'm afraid of the feedback so kahit na ngayon gano'n 'yung diagnosis na hindi nila alam. Medyo may mga feedback syempre na nakaka-hurt din given na anak mo 'yun. 'Yung gano'n. So, with the social life, okay naman parang treat things as normal lang pero deep inside, nando'n 'yung parang down na down. Sobrang down na talaga, pero 'di mo lang din pinapakita.</i></p>	The "newbie" parents.

Quality of life is as defined by the World Health Organization as an individual's assessment of their social standing, taking into consideration the influence of their culture and the system in which they exist. It consists of their place of residence, its correlation with their life objectives, aspirations, and worries. By inquiring about their personal lives, particularly after receiving the diagnosis for their child, parents demonstrated the profound impact that the condition has on their lives. Everyone began with acceptance and immediately devised a solution. As a result of this perception, these parents continue to assist their child daily as they did prior to learning the diagnosis, and they continue to do so. To assist other parents, one parent began sharing their experience of having a child with neurodevelopmental disorder and attempted to raise awareness about the condition.

Table 5. Coping Strategies of Parents

Theme	Statement	Informant
Coping strategies of parents	<i>Wala ka namang ibang ano eh, and then you help her, kung anong gusto n'ya, hindi mo na s'ya ipu-push sa mga ano.. Kasi dati meron tayong mga "Paglaki mo anak, gusto ko gan'to ka. Gusto ko..." Ako is kailangan kitang bilhan ng bahay para may bahay ka na kung mamatay ako. May bahay na. Dapat may savings ka na. Since it was ano na for me, , kumabaga I have an idea na kasi. It wasn't that hard for me to cope eh. So ano ako agad eh, action, gawin na natin 'to agad.</i>	The "coach" and the player.
	<i>Una talaga kailangan mong i-accept muna eh na ganon eh, may ganong sitwasyon eh kasi 'di ka makaka-move forward, 'di ka makaka-adjust sa mga bagay kung wala kang acceptance sa nangyari sa 'yo eh. Then, ah 'di ko masabi sa 'yo na talaga fully adjusted na kasi syempre minsan 'pag pagod, maraming ginagawa sa bahay tapos mangungulit s'ya, ganyan, minsan napapagalitan mo na s'ya. Siguro, 'yung learning process, ano 'yan habang tumatagal saka ka lang nakakapag-adjust nang maayos. So 'yun nga, 'di ko masabi sa 'yo na talaga fully okay na, pero ano ang masasabi ko lang, ah nasasanay na ko. Nakakapag-adjust naman ako one step at a time.</i>	The "coach" and the player.
	<i>How are we coping? Kini-kwento namin.. kunyare diba, yung mga friends ko. Na-kwento ko na to before na 'alam mo.. nagwo-worry ako kasi hindi pa sila nagsasalita hanggang nayon. ' ganun.. Diba, may mga ganun-ganun na scenario before? Tapos nung na-confirm na, yun.. 'uy confirmed. yung mga shine-share dun sa mga support system mo confirmed. Ganito.. Tapos kunyari yung sa center na napasukan namin before yung mga..may mga moments na parang hindi ako nag-aagree sa nangyari. Yung kwento ko din yun. Yun yung coping tsaka yung pag-sali sa mga group ng parents.</i>	The "super" nanay and tatay.
	<i>Number one na pumasok sa isip namin is parang tanggap namin. na ganun. Kung ano man yung problem sakanya, kung ano man yung hindi normal sakanya, talagang tanggap namin yun, and kaya nga namin ginagawa to ngayon is para at least, diba, magamot siya kahit pa onti-onti.</i>	Better late than never, parents.
	<i>Kasi number one lang naman dyan, kasi actually wala naman pong proper or right term for coping up. So number one is talagang ang pinaka number one dyan is talagang acceptance number one cure daw sa mga cases ng mga ganyan bata is acceptance of the parent. So ganun lang po talaga. Kailangan naming tanggapin, gawin kung ano yung advice ng therapist kung ano po yung dapat naming gawin sa bahay yung pag work on, kung pano po kami makakatulong. syempre hindi lang naman po natin dapat iasa sa therapist lahat e, diba?</i>	Better late than never, parents.
	<i>Hindi kami nagsisihan. Tinanggap... Syempre nung una, mahirap talagang tanggapin pero tinanggap na namin kasi kailangan eh. Kailangan sabi ko, "Tayo 'yung magulang. Kailangan tanggapin natin." Parang naaawa sa anak ko. Kaya nga sabi ko, "Hanggang dulo. Kung kaya... kung kailangan n'ya ng therapy, hanggang gumaling s'ya, go. Go talaga.</i>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
	<i>Alam mo ako kasi naniniwala talaga ako kay Lord na binigay n'ya sa 'kin 'to, alam ko malalagpasan natin 'to. Though 'yan lang talaga actually, pray lang talaga kami. Prayer lang talaga palagi ako. Sabi ko, alam ko hindi ako bibigyan ng problema na walang solusyon. Kasi 'pag 'di mo s'ya in-accept, wala. 'pag 'di mo in-accept, 'pag in denial ka, wala, wala talaga. Walang mangyayari. Sabi nga, 'wag nga daw matakot kung may gan'yan 'yung anak kasi isipin natin na blessing sila.</i>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay."
	<i>To tell you honestly, it's not that easy raising a child with this kind of situation, pero 'yun nga, sabi ko nga, hindi namin s'ya iniisip na gano'n eh. So more of normal pa rin, pero 'yun nga. 'Yung challenges, and 'yan na 'yan eh. Darating sa point na mawawalan talaga ng pasensya, but then again, maiisip mo, hindi you have to.. Hindi ka p'wedeng sumuko. You have to... Siguro 'yung patience mo, p'wede kaya 200% 'di ba?</i>	The "assertive" nanay and tatay.
	<i>They know na may problem pero laban lang kasi you have to be strong. Parang dapat hindi mo ipakita, and 'yun nga, I'm not that very... Disclosing on the status talaga. So parang usually parang okay naman. Ang daming tumutulong naman na they can help naman financially, and then 'yun nga kasi sobrang gastos din. Yung nangyari din made us kumbaga stronger pa 'yung faith kasi 'yun na talaga 'yung moment na wala ka namang magagawa kun'di give your best, 'yung mga therapy, gan'yan. Kumbaga it's a miracle na lang talaga for this one to be okay, and then coping up so ayun nga.</i>	The "newbie" parents.

Coping is an adaptive reaction to psychological strain, which is frequently instigated by life transitions. Additionally, it aids in the

maintenance of mental health and emotional stability. Cultivating coping strategies entails the adoption of behaviors, thoughts, and emotions that an individual must modify in response to life's changes (Jane & Terry, 2022). By coping, these parents can assist their offspring. They demonstrated the ability to alter their outlook on life as a coping mechanism. They began to embrace their child's condition and exert considerable effort to provide the necessary intervention. Most of them confided in friends and family about their difficulties to receive financial and emotional support. Other parents joined support groups comprised of parents with neurodevelopmental disorders to better comprehend and empathize with their children, as they have been through a similar journey. Other parents discovered a support system in these various support organizations, particularly those who struggle to disclose the diagnosis of their child to other members of their family.

Conclusion

The researcher concludes, after compiling the insights from the informant's statements and the four major themes, that the parents' coping strategies constitute the most important aspect of the study. Although the parents may employ various strategies to manage the difficulties, it is imperative that they acknowledge the circumstances and devise a course of action to facilitate their progress.

Based on the life stories of the informants and their experiences in having a newly diagnosed child with neurodevelopmental disorder, they are on a very challenging journey. However, they chose to see the silver lining and do the right thing. They chose to love their child even more and see the diagnosis as a blessing. In addition, these parents are doing their best to cope with everyday challenges. Like other people's lives, one must always choose to love and keep going even if things are not going our way. One should always accept things as they are and remember that there are, at times, not the way we expected them to be. Despite this, one should remember that better days will come if one believes.

In a research study, students should use and apply all the things learned in graduate school. All the years spent studying must reflect in the student's paper. Nevertheless, doing a research study is not just about the knowledge one acquires during the stay in school. Most importantly, as a Bedans, it should always come with a prayer. A core part of every Benedictine student- Prayer and Work. A person with these tools will surely be great and feel accomplished as one works with proper guidance and a pure heart.

Prayer is a person's weapon in any kind of situation. Through prayer, one will have clarity, a purpose, and peace of mind. Nothing is more significant than a person who always seeks the Lord's guidance and approval before doing something she wants. We must put God in the center of everything we will be doing, choosing, and thinking. We all have goals and ambitions that we all want to be fulfilled. The researcher is grateful to have these values and met people with the same views and beliefs, which helped this research be possible. The researcher will never forget all the things they learned and use this in everyday life.

References

- Alli, A., Abdoola, S., & Mupawose, A. (2015). Parents' journey into the world of autism. *SAJCH South African Journal of Child Health*. <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAJCH.7942>
- Caicedo, C. (2014). Families With Special Needs Children. *Journal of the American Psychiatric Nurses Association*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1078390314561326>
- Clayton, O., Chester, A., Mildon, R., & Matthews, J. (2008). Practitioners who work with parents with intellectual disability: Stress, coping and training needs. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3148.2008.00444.x>
- Dillenburger, K., Keenan, M., Doherty, A., Byrne, T., & Gallagher, S. (2010). Living with children diagnosed with autistic spectrum disorder: parental and professional views. *British Journal of Special Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8578.2010.00455>
- Gupta, V. B. (2007). Comparison of parenting stress in different developmental disabilities. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10882-007-9060-x>
- Johnson, N., Frenn, M., Feetham, S., & Simpson, P. (2011). Autism Spectrum Disorder: Parenting Stress, Family Functioning and Health-Related Quality of Life. *Families, Systems and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0025341>
- Kaniel, S., & Siman-Tov, A. (2011). Comparison between mothers and fathers in coping with autistic children: A multivariate model. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2011.597186>
- Kerr, S. M., & McIntosh, J. B. (2000). Coping when a child has a disability: Exploring the impact of parent-to-parent support. *Child: Care, Health and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2214.2000.00149.x>
- Kumar, V. G. (2008). Psychological stress and coping strategies of the parents of mentally challenged children. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*.
- Lustig, D. C. (2002). Family coping in families with a child with a disability. *Education and Training in Mental Retardation and Developmental Disabilities*.
- Luther, E. H., Canham, D. L., & Young Cureton, V. (2005). Coping and social support for parents of children with autism. *The Journal*

of School Nursing: The Official Publication of the National Association of School Nurses. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10598405050210010901>

McConkey, R., Truesdale-Kennedy, M., Chang, M. Y., Jarrah, S., & Shukri, R. (2008). The impact on mothers of bringing up a child with intellectual disabilities: A cross-cultural study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2006.08.007>

Moawad, G. E. N. a. (2012). Coping strategies of mothers having children with special needs. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare*.

Pepperell, T. A., Paynter, J., & Gilmore, L. (2018). Social support and coping strategies of parents raising a child with autism spectrum disorder. *Early Child Development and Care*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2016.1261338>

Redquest, B. K., Reinders, N., Bryden, P. J., Schneider, M., & Fletcher, P. C. (2015). Raising a child with special needs: The perspective of caregivers. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NUR.0000000000000122>

Shokoohi-Yekta, M., Ghobary-Bonab, B., Malayeri, S. A., Zamani, N., & Pourkarimi, J. (2015). The Relationship between Anger and Coping Strategies of Mothers of Children with Special Needs. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.09.041>

Tadema, A. C., & Vlaskamp, C. (2010). The time and effort in taking care for children with profound intellectual and multiple disabilities: A study on care load and support. *British Journal of Learning Disabilities*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3156.2009.00561.x>

Twoy, R., Connolly, P. M., & Novak, J. M. (2007). Coping strategies used by parents of children with autism. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse*

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Zyrene Anne A. Pabrualinan, MPsy
Lyceum of the Philippines - Philippines

Karen Marie P. Garcia, MAP-CP
National University - Philippines

Trixia Anne A. Reyes, MAP-CP
National University - Philippines